

FM

AM

State (using U = 5.1)	E-E _{FM} (meV/Unit cell)
AM	-34.788
AFM1	-55.007
AFM2	-53.159
AFM3	-42.664
FM	0.000

AFM1

AFM2

AFM3

Note :

- Because the competing magnetic ground states differ in energy by less than ~ 25 meV, thermal fluctuations may stabilize different magnetic configurations. Consequently, the realized magnetic state can depend sensitively on thin-film synthesis conditions. In the present work, ***we choose the altermagnetic state as a representative configuration*** and investigate the associated physical properties.